

CASE STUDY OF AN OCTAVE BAND CONTROL METHOD FOR STRUCTURAL RESPONSE NOTCHING

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Abstract

Spacecraft must be tested in acoustic environments by means of reverberant chamber tests (RFAN) or Direct Field Acoustic Tests (DFAN) where many speakers surround the test object. These tests require acoustic control software and matching hardware to drive the speakers with a controlled noise spectrum. Suppliers of such systems and test facilities are sometimes challenged with acoustic standing waves that create hotspots with higher than specified sound pressure levels that could damage the Device Under Test (DUT) by exciting structural resonances. As a safety measure to protect the DUT, a response limiting method (notching) is applied where critical frequencies in the acoustic spectrum are attenuated to keep the structural response levels limited.

This paper will present a detailed overview of a study which analyses the effects, benefits, and risks of utilizing mechanically coupled notching in both linear and nonlinear responses from both mechanically de-coupled acoustic environments. Analyzing structural response channels during Direct Field Acoustic Noise (DFAN) test can help to detect dangerous standing waves in the resulting sound field that can result from non-optimal speaker setup and control method.

Furthermore, notching on structural response channels can invalidate the test with respect to the specified octave test spectrum. A modified true octave band control method is used, which allows attenuation of narrowband frequencies while still meeting the general specification. The general applicability is discussed with respect to a “test like you fly” acoustic testing condition.

Introduction

2.1 Background on Spacecraft Acoustic Testing

Acoustic testing, which was first performed on NASA's Apollo Lunar Module in the 1960's, ensures that the spacecraft and its subsystems can withstand the violent acoustic loads encountered on launch. The method first used a progressive-wave form of acoustic excitation, and a duct system tailored to the outer fairing surrounding the Apollo Spacecraft [1]. Pressure waves from sixteen air modulators were directed through a transition horn, then a folded horn, and ultimately a duct-wall to achieve a directed acoustic field around the spacecraft as shown in Figure 1. This method was successful at achieving Overall Sound Pressure Levels (OASPL) of 152 dB for as long as forty-one seconds.

Figure 1 - Progressive Wave Design for NASA's Apollo Lunar Module [1]

Though the progressive method is still used to this day for highly concentrated, high Sound Pressure Level (SPL) tests, the nature of these types of facilities is highly specialized and is typically only built for specific environments.

2.2 Reverberant Field Testing

To accommodate a wider range of environments and Devices Under Test (DUT's), the space industry began to move toward specialized reverberant rooms made of structural reinforced concrete and many specialized, nitrogen-driven horns to produce broadband pressure waves. The pressure waves then reflected off the walls of the chamber, creating a diffuse sound field that approximated the intense acoustic conditions of a rocket launch. This became known as Reverberant Field Acoustic Noise testing (RFAN) and was the default method to simulate acoustic environments that spacecraft are exposed to during launch.

The primary advantage of RFAN testing lies in its ability to produce a high level of acoustic energy. The reverberant nature of the chamber allows relatively uniform pressure to be applied to the test object, which is critical for identifying potential weaknesses or workmanship issues with the structure.

However, RFAN tests are not without challenges. Though spectrally diffuse, the variations in amplitude and room-modes can lead to uneven control of sound pressure levels and less usable regions within the room. Additionally, the need for large, specialized facilities can make RFAN testing both expensive and logistically complex.

2.3 Legacy Direct Field Testing

Industry advancements in the 1990's began experimenting with using concert loudspeakers to perform tests. This offered the advantages of lower-cost and portability, which allowed testing to occur at nearly any location, reducing risk incurred when shipping spacecraft

This type of test became known as Direct Field Acoustic Noise testing (DFAN) and offered an alternative approach to RFAN with a more flexible and precise method of simulating launch environments. In DFAN setups, multiple speakers were positioned around the test object to create a controlled acoustic field.

Unlike RFAN, where sound energy is reflected off chamber walls, DFAN relied on the direct output of the speakers to generate the desired acoustic environment. Traditional loudspeakers, however, rely on summation to achieve the desired outputs (Typically between 138 and 150 dB OASPL) which can cause non-uniformities (interference patterns) in the field. Advanced control methods made uniformity better by attempting to control the phase or cross power of these standing waves, but they still had a finite number of independent drives [2] which will always produce a partially coherent field.

Early DFAN systems faced challenges in achieving uniformity and sound pressure level targets, primarily due to the usage of music reinforcement systems. Firstly, the loudspeakers required significant horizontal and vertical summation to achieve higher levels, which can cause an increase in interference patterns, causing less spatial uniformity. Secondly, because of the previous issue, expert placement of the DUT is necessary [3] to avoid non-uniform excitation of large flexural absorbers, like solar arrays. Lastly, the complexity of the systems and number of speakers needed required expert installation and operation from highly trained personnel and, sometimes, advanced simulation prior to testing.

2.4 Modern Direct Field Testing

To simplify this complex problem, a new type of device was designed with a simple premise: Make a full range device that can achieve launch levels independently so it could scale easily to more accurately approximate the ideal diffuse acoustic field, which can be defined as an infinite number of incoherent sources [2.] This device became known as the Neutron and was developed by Acoustic Research Systems. (ARS)

The Neutron is designed to be efficient in the band most used by launch vehicle acoustics, allowing it to achieve roughly 145 dB OASPL from a single device. Thus, it became possible to use many devices with incoherent sources to craft a diffuse field in a way that did not require A) specific placement of the speakers, B) special orientation of the DUT, or C) special mixing techniques from expert engineers [6.]

Figure 2 - Neutron Device - Front and Side Views

To expand on point A, this new device was different from typical loudspeakers because it was full range, meaning it covered the minimum and maximum frequencies required by a typical launch vehicle. As a result, there was no need to adjust the timing of separate band passes when changing the size

(Elevation and Diameter) of the test area. This, coupled with the fact that each Neutron could deliver sound from an incoherent and completely stochastic source, contributed to a more flexible and scalable field.

Addressing point B, the field produced by this type of system was found to be more spatially uniform when used with DUT's that are (or contain) large flexural absorbers. [5] This was partly because the stacks of Neutrons were not required to be coherent vertically and therefore did not produce large wavefronts [6] that rely on joint acceptance for excitation.

Lastly, to point C, the modular design of the Neutron device was such that any sized system could be deployed with the same level of complexity as a smaller one. Since a single Neutron connects with a single cable to one amplifier in a standardized rack, the deployment of stacks even twenty or forty feet tall are all wired the same way. Additionally, the control loops are simplified for this arrangement, as they treat each Neutron like a small acoustic field, so no advanced mixing is required.

3. LAUNCH QUALIFICATION

For both RFAN and DFAN tests, launch vehicle manufacturers provide their customers an acoustic environment, typically specified in 1/1 or 1/3 Octave band format, as part of a design qualification manual. These octave-based requirements are then simulated by one of the methods to create an acoustic field which is applied to a DUT.

Sometimes multiple launch vehicle spectra are combined if specifics about the launch are unknown at the time of testing. This is done simply by taking the maximum level at each octave or third-octave band and applying it to the overall test level, a practice known as enveloping. When using an enveloped environment, it is then determined by the spacecraft and launch vehicle manufacturers which type of test is most suited to the DUT.

In DFAN testing for spacecraft, different test levels - Flight, Protoflight, Protoqualification (Protoqual), and Qualification - are applied depending on the needs of the DUT. For routine tests, Flight testing can be performed at the exact levels expected during the mission to validate the flight hardware, with no added margin. More typically for routine products, Protoflight testing is used, which combines elements of Qualification and Flight testing, adding a small margin (typically +3 dB) to ensure the hardware's robustness while still being conservative with respect to the flight hardware.

For first-production DUT's, Protoqualification testing can serve as an intermediate step, testing at levels between flight and qualification or for

longer durations than Protoflight to validate new designs or manufacturing changes. Qualification test levels are the most rigorous, exposing non-flight units to levels significantly above what is expected during the mission (often +6 dB) to uncover potential weaknesses. This ensures that the design is robust enough to handle worst-case scenarios, though the hardware used in these tests is usually not always intended for actual flight.

3.1 DFAN Notching

Many DUT's, especially fully assembled spacecraft, are best served when testing as they are meant to fly, wherein little modification is made to the acoustic environment. Sometimes, however, portions of the spectrum are modified to attenuate specific frequencies in a practice known as "notching."

One such case of notching would have been considered when utilizing legacy DFAN testing systems. In this case, a spacecraft manufacturer may have considered notching when there is a risk that standing waves could induce structural resonances that might damage sensitive components of the spacecraft. Particularly when using speakers which follow the design of a typical concert line array source, which rely on coherence to achieve the 140 to 150 dB OASPL environments, interference patterns can develop. These interference patterns appear as spectrally dependent high/low spots in the field which can overexcite structural modes, causing excessive vibrations that could compromise the integrity of the spacecraft or its subsystems. Notching has been employed as a protective measure to attenuate these frequencies on critical components, thereby preventing over-stressing of the spacecraft structure.

Modern DFAN testing methods, such as the one used for this experiment, are designed to attain launch levels with minimal summation. In this type of environment, the spatial uniformity is such that the need to notch would only be necessary if conditions of the DUT are compromised.

For example, a spacecraft assembled with all components intended for flight will benefit from testing exactly to the envelope (Plus the desired qualification level, if required) without any component notches, because this is most likely to represent the actual launch environment.

Sometimes in the manufacturing process, a DUT may have one or more components which are not flight-like, such as mass mock-ups or development units. These development units may be used for convenience or some other production constraint. Either way, the structural response from a standard environment may induce damage that would not occur in-flight

because the coupled load between the mock-up and DUT are different than that of the flight units.

It is precisely this condition that may require a field with diffuse acoustic properties to attenuate, or notch, at certain frequencies based on a structural response.

4. CONTROL METHODS

4.1 Narrowband Control

Legacy control strategies for Direct Field Acoustic Noise testing employ a modified random-vibration control method. This type of control strategy utilizes weighted exponential averaging of field measurements which must undergo Fast Fourier Transformations (FFT's) and conversion to Power Spectral Density (PSD) before the averaging functions are applied. This process, as well as the exponential averaging, slows the controller's ability to react to changes in the acoustic field significantly. For notching, however, the process provides a simple basis of control already designed to notch acceleration signals for a mechanically coupled vibration test.

This method of control makes it possible to easily apply notches to the field, but controllability suffers, as it is reliant on a slower exponential averaging technique and phase targeting that severely limit the number of available outputs. This works well for smaller tests that only need twelve Neutron devices but does not scale well for tests which require many more devices, such as one hundred to two-hundred devices.

4.2 Octave Control

A second version of acoustic control is based on one-third octave processing and has been used to some success in RFAN environments for decades. This method uses multiple overlapping Finite Impulse Response (FIR) filters to quickly determine the ultimate pressure at each octave or third-octave band. This process can happen in one second or less, controlling rapid changes to the field, potentially from power fluctuations or structural response, immediately.

Figure 3 - Example - Octave Control Method

This method has been shown to be more scalable as, currently, forty-eight or more outputs can be combined to produce a field which is closer to the ideal diffuse acoustic field. This is more easily done because there is no need to control the phase or cross power between loops, as doing so exponentially increases the required processing power to complete a test

Within this octave-band control method, however, did not exist a method for notching the acoustic field from acceleration responses on a DUT. It was posited by the authors that some combination of the above two methods would provide more accurate and stable technique by controlling octaves but notching in the narrowband, with both occurring in the same control system. This method could even prioritize the spectral response of the one third octave band requirements by boosting un-notched frequencies within each band where notching is present. In this way, the test could maintain not just the overall sound pressure level, but also each individual octave band as required by the launch manual. The following test aims to examine this method of notching.

5. TEST METHODOLOGY

Though very little is published on the subject, notching acoustic fields for DFAN is not a novel concept. There have been tests where attenuation was applied to flight DUT's with some success. For these cases, however, a narrowband vibration control strategy was used to control the field as well as apply the notch. Due to the advantages of controlling in the one-third octave, this study focused on using an octave band control method for the control algorithm but also used a narrowband process to apply the attenuation. In short, this test was designed to determine whether it's possible to use an octave-band control method to maintain the test requirements while attenuating the field in the narrowband.

5.1 Test Configuration

The authors originally planned to perform two separate tests to determine whether the objective of the study could be achieved. Due to the results of the second configuration, as will be evident later in this report, a third was added. Ultimately, three configurations were used and will be referred to as the following when presenting results:

- 01: No Notching Applied
- 02: Notching Applied
- 03: Adjusted (deeper) Notching Applied

5.2 Test Article

Typically, the test article is a complex structure to which notching will be applied. For this study, however, a simple aluminum honeycomb panel with epoxy edge treatment was used to simplify the analysis. This also provided a worst-case scenario where the test article is nearly undamped at several critical frequencies. Physically, the panel was 96" x 48" x .5" and had four mounting points for which to affix to a frame made of extruded aluminum. To measure the response of the panel, five Kistler triaxial accelerometers (3.6 gram) were used and mounted as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 – Test Panel – Accelerometer Locations

5.3 Acoustic Devices and Test Levels

To excite the test article adequately and uniformly, a configuration of eight stacks of three Neutron devices from Acoustic Research systems were used. The system was controlled in a completely 'incoherent' state, which is to say that each Neutron device produced output from twenty to ten-thousand hertz with twenty-four completely stochastic drive signals. By driving the system this way, the field was assured to be as spatially uniform as possible, as no assumptions are being made about phase-control at specific control locations.

Figure 5: Test Photo - Neutron Devices Surrounding the Test Panel

A test level of 143.2 dB overall sound-pressure level at a duration of one minute was used for all test configurations and is detailed in Table 1.

Table 1- Test Levels

Octave Center	Level (dB)	Alarm Low	Alarm High	Abort High
20	115.4	-3	3	6
25	120.7	-3	3	6
31.5	125.5	-3	3	6
40	130.1	-3	3	6
50	131.5	-3	3	6
63	132.8	-3	3	6
80	133.5	-3	3	6
100	133.8	-3	3	6
125	134.2	-3	3	6
160	134	-3	3	6
200	134	-3	3	6
250	132.2	-3	3	6
315	130.1	-3	3	6
400	127.4	-3	3	6
500	124.8	-3	3	6
630	122.4	-3	3	6
800	119.1	-3	3	6
1000	116.3	-3	3	6
1250	112.9	-3	3	6
1600	109.1	-3	3	6
2000	106.4	-3	3	6
2500	103.6	-3	3	6
3150	101	-3	3	6
4000	98	-3	3	6
5000	95.1	-3	3	6
6300	92.2	-3	3	6
8000	89.4	-3	3	6
10000	86.9	-3	3	6
OASPL	143.2	-1	1	3

5.4 Equipment

To conduct each test case, numerous equipment and instrumentation were used. Firstly, to control each of the twenty-four loops, a pre-polarized microphone assembly (PCB 378A12) consisting of a capsule and an amplification unit were used. These microphones were calibrated just prior to testing using a National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) calibrated acoustic source (Larson Davis CAL200,) which compensated for local altitude, temperature, and humidity.

To acquire the test panel response, five Kistler 8763 series accelerometers were used due to their low mass (3.6 grams) and flexible mounting options.

To power the twenty-four individual Neutron units, an ARS Core Rack was used for each grouping of six, totaling four. The control unit consisted of an ARS Drive, which uses six VRAI810 units from m+p International to convert the sensor voltages to digital data for both control and data acquisition, as well as six VRT4S4 units to provide twenty-four independent source outputs. These sources are then digitized for input to the DirectOut PRODIGY.MP unit, a commercial audio routing processor, to route the source signals to the Neutron devices.

All data for each test case was taken at a sample rate of 32,768 and processed with blocks of the same size, producing PSD measurements with sixty averages and at 1 Hz resolution. Octave plots were generated in the same way but using the ANSI standard for 1/3 octave processing. The charts for all octave responses include a nominal reference line (green) with upper and lower tolerances of +/- 3 dB (orange) and an upper abort tolerance of +6 dB (red) for clarity.

Table 2 - Test Equipment List

Item #	Description	Manufacturer	Model	QTY
1	Prepolarized Microphone Assembly	PCB	378A12	24
2	Microphone Calibrator	Larson Davis	CAL200	1
3	IEPE Triaxial Accelerometer - 3.6 gram	Kistler	8763B36	5
4	Acoustic Device - Full Range Neutron	ARS	Neutron 104	24
5	Amplification Unit - 6 Devices	ARS	Core Rack	4
6	Control Unit - ARS, m+p DF-ACS	ARS	Drive	1
7	A/D Conversion Module	m+p International	VRAI810	6
8	Analog Source Module	m+p International	T4S4	6
9	Audio Conversion/Routing Unit	DirectOut	PRODIGY.MC	1

6. RESULTS

6.1 Pre-Notch Evaluation

Before applying the notch, the test profile from Table 1 was applied without attenuation to determine the overall panel response. The panel appeared to be minimally damped, with roughly sixteen lowly damped modes appearing between 25 and 2000 Hz. Three such modes were chosen specifically for notching, with a fourth designed to encompass a bandwidth, or several peaks simultaneously. This notch was intended to capture and attenuate three or more modes with a single setting. Of the five accelerometer locations, the four most reactive axes from A01, A02, A04 and A05 were chosen for the notch.

In Figure 6 below, a PSD from the z-axis response of four accelerometer locations is shown. The vertical lines indicate the center frequencies for the first, second, and third notch. For the fourth notch, the vertical lines indicate the upper and lower frequencies of the bandwidth. The red horizontal lines indicate the initial setting in g^2/Hz for all notches.

Figure 6 - Panel Response - Notch Selections

The initial settings for the notches are more precisely described in Table 3. For each accelerometer channel, the notch is defined by a starting frequency (Notch Low, in the table below,) an ending frequency (Notch High) and a single value in g^2/Hz (Notch 01) for flat notches or two values for sloped notches, with the starting and ending numbers appearing respectively.

Also in Table 3 are the precise values for the peaks as measured by the pretest evaluation run. For example, channel A01_Z indicated a peak value of 8.797 g2/Hz at a frequency of 98 Hz and the notch setting was set to 2g2/Hz between 93 and 105 Hz. The results of these settings will be described in the following section.

Table 3 - Notch Settings

Channel	Name	Notch Low (Hz)	Notch High (Hz)	Peak Value - No notch (g2/Hz)	Notch 01 (g2/Hz)
35	A01_Z	93	105	8.797	2
38	A02_Z	37	49	1.6	0.8
41	A03_Z	204	222	14.445	2
47	A05_Z	346	450	1, 0.3, 0.2	0.2, 0.1

6.2 Acoustic Notching Results 01

Similarly to the pre-notch evaluation, the acoustic profile in Table 1 was applied to the panel for a duration of sixty seconds. Prior to the full-level portion of the test, a -3 dB level was achieved for fifteen seconds. During that level, the channels began to notch allowing the field to start attenuation before jumping to the next level. This is a recommended practice to avoid over-testing the DUT.

Figure 7 - Control Average PSD - Without Notch vs. With Notch

In Figure 7 above, the blue trace depicts the average PSD of the control microphones without notching applied and the red trace is the same but with notching.

Presumably due to the undamped nature of the panel, the applied notches yielded ultimate values that were above that of the prescribed notch, as shown in Figure 8 below.

Figure 8 - A01_Z Without vs With Notch Applied

With a notch of 2 g²/Hz applied from 93 to 105 Hz, the actual value was reduced from 8.8 g²/Hz to 6.1 g²/Hz. Though a reduction of about thirty percent, the ultimate value was above the prescribed notch. It is not uncommon for narrowband notches, especially in vibration testing, to overshoot their settings and can depend on a number of factors including but not limited to a) the delta frequency of the spectral lines in control, b) the speed at which the control averages update, and c) the quality (q) factor of the peak to be notched.

Similarly to the A01_Z example, the rest of the notched channels exceeded their prescribed values, as shown in Table 4.

Table 4 - Measured Notch Values 01

Name	Notch Low (Hz)	Notch High (Hz)	Peak Value - No notch (g2/Hz)	Notch 01 (g2/Hz)	Peak Value Notch 01 (g2/Hz)
A01_Z	93	105	8.797	2	6.13
A02_Z	37	49	1.6	0.8	1.449
A03_Z	204	222	14.445	2	5.87
A05_Z	346	450	1, 0.3, 0.2	0.2, 0.1	0.5, 0.2, 0.18

Though the notching values of the control average, when viewed in PSD, exceeded their lower limits, the goal of this exercise was to determine if the individual octave bands could be achieved while simultaneously notching the test article.

When the same data in Figure 7 was processed in one third octaves, it was observed that this goal was achieved. By slightly boosting the narrowband lines within the octave-bands that had notches applied, the overall spectrum was unchanged from the pre-test run without any notching applied. In Figure 9 the blue trace with no notch is almost identical to the red trace with notching applied.

Figure 9 - Control Average 1/3 Octave - Without Notch vs. With Notch

Though the overall goal was achieved in this experiment, it was decided by the authors to modify the notch settings to see if the initial values could be achieved at or below the prescribed levels, while still maintaining the integrity of the one-third octave band requirements.

6.3 Acoustic Notching Results 02

To achieve the initial notch values, each was adjusted to below the intended target. In Figure 10, the initial notch values are darkened to blue with the adjusted values appearing in red. Note that Notch Four's beginning and ending values were flattened, so some overshoot was still expected within that region.

Figure 10 - Panel Response - Adjusted Notch Settings

With the test applied exactly as before but with the adjusted settings, as shown in Figure 11, the resulting acoustic field was much more attenuated within the ranges which were notched. It was also noted that the regions around the notches were boosted by the control algorithm more than in the previous run to maintain the one-third octave requirements. This is especially true in the notch with the lowest frequency (centered around 42 Hz) as there are less lines of resolution to resolve.

Figure 11 - Control Average PSD - Without Notch vs. With Adjusted Notch

Overall, the results of the adjusted notch were much more favorable in terms of not exceeding the prescribed notch. For example, the A01_Z measurement, which originally targeted 2 g²/Hz now achieved a peak value of 1.7 g²/Hz with a notch setting of 0.5 g²/Hz as shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12 - A01_Z With Adjusted Notch Applied

This trend was consistent with the rest of the notches save the very last value, as shown in Table 5, but this was expected due to the flattened nature of the fourth notch.

Table 5 - Measured Notch Values 02

Name	Notch Low (Hz)	Notch High (Hz)	Notch 01 (g2/Hz)	Notch 02 (g2/Hz)	Peak Value Notch 02 (g2/Hz)
A01_Z	93	105	2	0.5	1.65
A02_Z	37	49	0.8	0.1	0.33
A03_Z	204	222	2	1	1.4
A05_Z	346	450	0.2, 0.1	0.1	0.2, 0.18, 0.17

Similarly to the original notch test, the adjusted notch values produced 1/3 octave results that were nearly unchanged from the requirement as shown in Figure 13. Only the one octave band centered at 31.5 Hz measured at slightly higher than the three-decibel upper tolerance, though it is common for tests which are performed in reverb chambers to allow for a six-decibel tolerance in this band, so this is a somewhat typical deviation. This slight deviation was likely due to the lack of spectral lines available for which to both a) notch the response channel in the narrowband, and b) boost the remaining frequencies within the one-third octave band to maintain the test requirements. This can easily be remedied by increasing the delta frequency in the narrowband processing, which is a proposed improvement because of this study.

Figure 13 - Control Average 1/3 Octave - Without Notch vs. With Adjusted Notch

The following figures show the additional plots of notches two through four in more detail.

In Figure 14 the original target of 0.8 g²/Hz was attenuated to 0.33 g²/Hz at 42 Hz. Note the slightly increased response at 30 Hz, which is an artifact of the algorithm attempting to maintain specification in the octave band.

Figure 14 - A02_Z - PSD - Adjusted Notch

In Figure 15 the original target of 2 g²/Hz was attenuated to 1.4 g²/Hz at 216 Hz.

Figure 15 - A03_Z - PSD - Adjusted Notch

In Figure 16 the original target from 0.2 g²/Hz at 346 Hz to 0.1 g²/Hz at 450 Hz, three separate peaks were reduced to 0.2, 0.18, and 0.17 g²/Hz at 360, 390, and 428 Hz, respectively.

Figure 16 - A05_Z - PSD - Adjusted Notch

CONCLUSION & FORWARD WORK

Notching in acoustic fields is not new and has been used in several testing situations. It is somewhat new, however, to notch in narrowband while controlling the output levels in one-third octaves to match the original specifications. In this study, both were achieved using the same control system and some observations were made.

Firstly, it is indeed possible to maintain the one-third octave specification for a DFAN test while still applying relatively deep structural attenuation in the narrowband. By boosting the frequencies within the one-third octave band that remain after a notch is applied, the specification can be maintained.

Secondly, similarly to a random vibration test with lowly-damped articles, the ultimate setting of the notch value needs to be considered in terms of the amount of damping on the test article. Since this test was performed with a highly reactive panel, the typical damping of a more structurally complex DUT did not exist. There exist some post processing techniques to invert the overshoot of the notch, as in the m+p VibControl software for Random Vibration Testing, which are effective at preventing overshoot and this can be done with basic analysis to create a more well-defined notch.

Looking back to the original progressive-wave test performed on the Apollo Lunar Module, which was made at great expense to simulate only a single environment, it seems pragmatic to continue evolving testing to more expansive and reusable means. This extends, even, to test articles from one iteration to another, as described in this paper, where notching may be required for attenuation.

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